

THE USE OF STEM TECHNOLOGY IN THE TEACHING OF NATURAL SCIENCES

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Abstract. The use of STEM technology in the teaching of natural sciences helps to strengthen students' knowledge and clear decision-making. It is easy to model each organ and study its functioning. The movement of the fingers and the functioning of the heart and lungs are easily explained by the integration of biological and physical sciences.

Keywords: STEM, model, integration, heart, lungs, hand movement

Annotatsiya. Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda STEM texnologiyalaridan foydalanish o'quvchining bilimini mustahkamlanishiga va aniq qarorlar chiqarishiga yordam beradi. Har bir organni modellashtirib, uning ishlash jarayonlarini oson o'rganish mumkin. Qo'l barmoqlarini harakatlantirish, yurak va o'pkaning ishlash jarayonini biologiya va fizika fanlarining integratsiyasi orqali oson tushuntiriladi.

Аннотация. Использование STEM технологии в преподавании естественных наук помогает укрепить знания учащихся и принять обоснованное решения. Каждый орган легко смоделировать и изучить его функционирование. Движение пальцев, работу сердца и легких легко объяснить с помощью интеграции биологических и физических наук.

When mastering science, theoretical knowledge is strengthened by practice, and if the acquired knowledge is applied in life, the intended result is achieved. Nowadays, it is necessary for students to use STEM technologies widely so that they can apply the knowledge they have acquired in life. STEM = Science + Technology + Engineering + Mathematics. The joint use of these subjects encourages the students to think creatively and use their knowledge in the right situation.

The use of STEM technologies in the teaching of natural sciences helps to increase the educational content, strengthen the students' knowledge and clear decision-making.

STEM technologies can be applied to subjects taught to students in anatomy. For example, the human locomotor system can be studied through a model showing the bending of fingers. For this, cardboard paper, plastic straws, thread, scotch tape, pencil, scissors are needed. Modeling is done in the following sequence:

1. A copy is drawn by placing the hand on the cardboard paper.
2. Cardboard cutout is made by cutting paper.
3. Plastic straws are cut into smaller tubes and the tubes are taped to fit finger phalanges.

Two tubes are attached to the thumb and three to the other fingers.

4. Longer cut tubes are glued to the palm. They act as finger bones.

5. Turn the back of the arm and attach a thread to the tip.
6. A thread is passed through each tube. The tip of the thread is made to fit a finger.
7. By inserting the fingers into the string and bending them, the palm model can be set in motion as a result of bending and unbending.

When studying the circulatory system, creating a heart model helps to visualize its working process. For this, a glass jar, water, red paint, a balloon, two plastic straws, scotch tape and plasticine are needed.

1. Fill the jar with water and add paint.
2. Cut the bottom part of the balloon and cover the top of the jar with a balloon.
3. Secure the edge of the balloon with tape.
4. Cut a small hole in the balloon and lower the straw.
5. Seal the part attached to the balloon using the plasticine so that air does not enter.
6. Press the balloon and watch the water come out of the straw.

The students easily model the pumping of blood from the heart to the blood vessels in the experiment and remember the process of the experiment. In understanding this topic, the knowledge gained from physics and chemistry is also strengthened.

When studying the respiratory system, creating a model of the lungs helps to understand the subject easily. Two small balloons, one large balloon, one plastic bottle, plastic straws, scotch tape, leucoplaster, scissors are necessary for the experiment.

1. Attach small balloons to the ends of the straws and fasten them with tape.
2. Cut the bottom of the bottle. Cut the large balloon in half and attach it to the cut part of the bottle.
3. Lower the balloon tubes into the bottle. Pierce the cap and attach the tube to it.
4. Close the lid tightly and pull the big balloon down.
5. Release the balloon and watch the change.

This experiment shows the process of air entering the lungs as a result of pressure changes. The use of STEM technologies in the course of the lesson inspires students to be interested in science, to search, to think critically, and to work in a team.

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